

Potentiometric and Polarographic Studies of Uranyl Acrylate System

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The complexation of uranyl ion with acrylic acid was investigated by potentiometry and polarography. One complex, UO_2Acryl^+ was obtained. The dissociation and the formation constants of the acid and of the complex obtained from potentiometry were $pK_a=4.25$ and $\log K=2.77$, respectively. Two waves were observed for the reduction of the complex in the pH range 1.8–4.5 with the consumption of one and two electrons through the first and the second wave respectively. Anomalous adsorption wave was observed near pH 2.6. A reduction mechanism has been proposed.

NUMEROUS reports have been published on the equilibria of various complexes formed between uranyl ion and carboxylic acids. However, the studies on the complexes of uranyl ion with unsaturated organic acids are lacking¹. Copper(II) complexes of some unsaturated acids, including acrylic acid, were investigated by Edmondson and Lever². Acrylic acid was used as anhydrous solvent for the examination of the voltammetric behaviour of copper(II), copper(I), cadmium, lead(II), thallium(I) and silver ions³. The possibility of complex formation between uranyl ion and acrylic acid was explored in the present work using potentiometric and polarographic methods.

Experimental

A 1M acrylic acid was prepared as stock solution from purified⁴ sample (B.D.H.) using double-distilled water. The acid was then standardised alkalimetrically. Uranyl perchlorate prepared by repeated evaporation of uranyl nitrate (G.R., Merck) with $HClO_4$, was dissolved in water (100 ml) to give a 0.1 M solution. The exact uranium concentration of the solution was determined by gravimetry⁴ as U_3O_8 .

Procedure: The experimental method consisted of potentiometric measurements of H^+ ion concentration of the solution of the acrylic acid in the presence of and in the absence of UO_2^{2+} . The potentiometric titrations were carried out in a jacketed beaker through which water at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ was circulated. The total volume was made up to 100 ml with distilled water. The mixture was titrated with standard 0.1 N NaOH (carbonate-free) in nitrogen atmosphere. The titration was made for $[Ligand] : [Uranyl] = 1 : 4$. A Radiometer WGPY 290 pH meter, fitted with combined glass and calomel electrodes, was used in the measurement of the pH. All the measurements were made in presence of 0.1 M $NaClO_4$.

Polarograms were taken at 25' using a capillary at a flow rate of 1.97 mg s^{-1} and a drop time of 3.6 s in 0.1 M KCl (open-circuit) using a LP 60 polarograph. The polarographic measurements were carried out in presence of 0.1 M $HClO_4$ to which increments of NaOH were added to adjust pH of the supporting electrolyte.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric titrations: Potentiometric titration curves of the ligand and the solutions containing 1:2 and 1:1 molar ratios of uranyl ion to acrylic acid are illustrated in Fig. 1. Separation of solid phase was observed above pH 5 and the titrations are represented by dotted curves. It shows that the metal-titration curve is well separated from the ligand-titration curves; thus the liberation of protons is due to the complexation. Moles of

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration of acrylic acid in presence of UVI; (a) $4.65 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ acid, (b) $4.65 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ acid + $4.65 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ UVI and (c) $4.65 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ acid + $2.32 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ UVI.

alkali per mole of uranium salt indicate that the single proton in the acid is replaced by one uranyl ion. The liberation of the proton may be explained by the reaction,

The calculations of the stability constant of the formed complex and the formation constant of the ligand-proton system were made by Irving and Rossotti's difference method⁵. The values of \bar{n}_H (average number of H^+ ions attached per ligand) are plotted against pH in Fig. 2. Interpolation at half \bar{n}_H value gives a value of $\log \beta^H$; the protonation constant of the ligand equals to 4.25, which is the same as reported⁶.

Fig. 2. Formation curve of proton - acrylic acid system.

The metal - ligand stability constants are obtained from the analysis of metal - ligand formation curve (Fig. 3), i.e. plots between \bar{n} (average number of ligands attached per metal ion) and pL (free ligand exponent). Interpolation at half \bar{n} value ($\bar{n}=0.5$)

Fig. 3. Formation curve of UVI - acrylic acid system.

gives a value of 2.77 for $\log K$, where K is the conditional formation constant of the complex ($H_2C=CHCOOUO_2$)⁺. No data for stability constant for uranyl - acrylate complexes are available in literature for comparison. However, a value of $\log K=2.77$ for the uranyl acrylate complex is higher

than the corresponding 1:1 uranyl formate complex. The stability constant of the latter was calculated¹ to be $\log K=2.61$ under the same conditions. Comparing pK values of acrylic acid and formic acid (4.25 and 3.54, respectively) it may be concluded that the higher stability constant of uranyl acrylate complex is due to the higher basicity of the ligand as well as the presence of double bond in the structure. There is a possibility to say that there is an interaction between the uranyl ion and the olefinic linkage although there is a little tendency towards this type of interaction with some other metals (e.g. Cu^{2+} and Ag^+) on mixing with similar unsaturated organic acid, for instance, crotonic acid⁷.

Polarographic behaviour of uranyl - acrylate system: The polarographic reduction of 1 mM uranyl perchlorate in 0.1 M $HClO_4$ as supporting electrolyte gave two waves with $E_{1/2}$ values equal to -0.178 and -0.840 V vs S.C.E., the height of the second wave being twice that of the first wave. These waves correspond to the reduction of U^{VI} to U^V and the reduction of U^V to U^{III} via one- and two-electron reduction steps, respectively, as reported earlier⁸.

On adding acrylic acid, a slight shift occurs in the two waves to more negative potentials. The more negative potentials for the reduction of UO_2^{2+} in presence of acrylic acid compared to those in perchloric acid alone, indicate the complex formation between uranyl ion and acrylic acid. The polarographic characteristics are presented in Table 1. It is clear that the first wave exhibits

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF URANYL ACRYLATE COMPLEX

C_{HL} M	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)		Slope of log plot 1st	i_d (μA)		Slope of log h vs log i plot	
	1st	2nd		1st	2nd	1st	2nd
0.00	0.178	0.840	0.059	3.0	6.0	0.51	0.50
0.01	0.190	0.860	0.061	3.1	5.9	0.52	0.53
0.03	0.193	0.880	0.062	2.9	4.9	0.57	0.58
0.04	0.195	0.895	0.064	3.0	4.4	0.57	0.57
0.07	0.198	0.914	0.071	3.0	4.4	0.57	0.58
0.18	0.200	0.925	0.075	2.9	4.4	0.57	0.58

reversible character in absence of acrylic acid and the reversibility decreases on increasing the concentration of acrylic acid above 0.04 M. The second reduction wave of U^{VI} appears to have an irreversible character since the slopes of the log analysis of the waves are in the range 0.05 - 0.07.

The slopes of log h vs log i plots (0.51 - 0.58), indicate that the electroreduction processes represented by the first and second waves are diffusion-controlled. The effect of concentration of UO_2^{2+} was studied in 0.1 M $HClO_4$ and in presence of 0.01 and 0.1 M acrylic acid solutions. A concentration range 0.4 - 2.4 mM UO_2^{2+} indicates that Ilkovic equation is obeyed along the first and the second waves.

Effect of pH on polarography of uranyl ion in acrylate solutions : The effect of pH on the electroreduction of uranyl ion in 0.1 M acrylic acid and in presence of 0.1 M HClO₄ as supporting electrolyte was studied in the pH range 1.8–4.5. The desired pH values of the solutions were attained by the additions of freshly prepared 0.1 M sodium hydroxide (carbonate-free) solution. An appropriate volume of NaClO₄ was added to keep the ionic strength constant at 0.2. The recorded polarograms are shown in Fig. 4. The $E_{1/2}$ values of both the first and second reduction steps of U^{VI} shifted to more negative potentials on increasing pH of the solution, however, an anomalous wave with $E_{1/2} = -0.5$ V appeared at pH 2.4–2.7 ; thus the polarogram consists of three waves.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on polarography of 1 mM UO₂⁺ - 0.1 M acrylic acid at pH : (a) 1.83, (b) 2.55, (c) 3.58, (d) 3.89 and (e) 4.49.

The polarographic data of the electroreduction of U^{VI} at different pH values are listed in Table 2. The slopes of the logarithmic analysis indicate that the first wave is reversible at lower pH and becomes less reversible on increasing pH of the solution, viz. pH > 3. The second wave exhibits an irreversible character in the entire pH range. The effect of mercury height, as gathered from the slopes of log h vs log i plots, indicates that the first and second waves are diffusion-controlled.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF pH ON POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF URANYL ACRYLATE COMPLEX (0.1 M ACRYLIC ACID+0.1 M HClO₄)

pH	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)		Slope of log plot	i_d (μ A)		Slope of log h vs log i plot	
	1st	2nd		1st	2nd	1st	2nd
1.83	0.184	0.925	0.060	3.0	5.8	0.50	0.53
2.55	0.187	1.100	0.062	3.0	5.2	0.54	0.58
3.58	0.255	1.205	0.138 ^a	3.1	2.8	0.60	—
3.89	0.265	1.220	0.075	3.1	2.4	0.66	—
4.49	0.315	1.300	0.078	3.1	1.6	0.66	—

^aAnomalous adsorption wave.

The nature of the anomalous wave becomes clear from the value of the slopes of log h vs log i plots which is 0.73. Also, from the effect of concentration of UO₂²⁺ at pH 2.7, this wave can be ascribed as an adsorption wave since the limiting currents become constant at concentrations of U^{VI} > 1 mM. Furthermore, this wave appears at the expense of the second reduction step of U^{VI}. Therefore, this wave may be attributed to the adsorption of the product of the species that reduced along the second reduction step of U^{VI}, i.e. appears as an adsorption pre-wave. The limiting current of the first wave remains almost constant on increasing pH of the solution. On the other hand, current of the second reduction wave of U^{VI} decreases on increasing the pH. This may be due to the hydrolysis of U^V species and/or the formation of non-reducible U^V species.

On plotting $E_{1/2}$ vs pH for the first wave, a straight line is obtained with two sections having the slopes zero and 0.064 (Fig. 5). These two sections cover the pH ranges 1.8–2.6 and 2.6–4.5, respectively. The slope of the first section indicates that no proton is involved in the reduction process,

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on $E_{1/2}$ of the reduction of 1 mM UO₂⁺ in 0.1 M acrylic acid.

whereas the second section reveals that one proton is consumed. For the second reduction wave of U^{VI}, the slope of the $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plot is 0.14, indicating that two protons are consumed in the entire pH range.

Effect of acrylic acid concentration at constant pH : The plots of the value of log C_{Acryl} vs $E_{1/2}$ of the first wave, reveal straight lines (Fig. 6). The slopes of these lines are 0.0 and 0.045 for the first wave at pH 1.8 and 4.3, respectively ; in case of the second wave the values are 0.06 and 0.05. Using these values and the corresponding values of $\Delta E_{1/2}/\Delta pH$ and substituting in the polarographic equation of complex reduction⁹, the reduction of uranyl acrylate complex (first wave) may be stated

Fig. 6. Effect of acrylic acid concentration on $E_{1/2}$ of the reduction of 1 mM UO_2^{+} at constant pH.

as follows : at $\text{pH} < 2.6$,

and at $\text{pH} > 2.6$, the following reaction predominates,

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